

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

SWOT ANALYSIS ON THE REMOTE WORKING IN THE BASILICATA REGION [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 3

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OBJECTIVE 1

Research module 1 (New remote working tools and devices)

Identification of wants and needs, local opportunities, strengths, and solutions for effective and efficient remote working in firms located in the Basilicata region.

INTRODUCTION

The territory: fragility and opportunity

Basilicata has a highly varied territory (almost 70% mountainous, 22% hilly and only 8% flat) in its morphological and naturalistic sense but it can be said to be predominantly mountainous due to the presence of the Apennine ridge which crosses the region in its western part, from north to south. In fact, the Lucanian Apennines begin on the border with Campania, close to the Marzano-Eremita Mountains Reserve, and shield the entire region up to the “Pollino” National Park, where the highest peaks are located. The region is characterized by intense erosion and constant instability of the slopes, also accentuated by the strong seismicity of the area; landslides are very widespread and make Basilicata the region with the highest number of damaged or depopulated municipalities. For this reason, the most of Basilicata inner areas face various infrastructural problems, where the orography of the territory, typical of mountain areas, hinders economic development, accessibility to services and the quality of life of residents. The mountain territory of the inner areas therefore significantly affects the regional economy, the natural environment and recreational activities. The recovery of inner areas contributes to reducing economic and social inequalities between Italian regions, promoting a more equitable distribution of resources and opportunities. Many Basilicata inner areas are characterized by uncontaminated natural landscapes, unique historical and cultural heritage and local traditions. Recovery helps preserve and enhance these precious resources, while promoting sustainable practices useful for conserving the natural environment and mitigating climate change. Inland areas often host unique local resources, such as quality agriculture, traditional craftsmanship and typical productions, which when inserted into new employment circuits are able to create local economic opportunities, contribute to the well-being of communities and avoid depopulation, preserving their human capital. Policies to relaunch inner areas underpin long-term strategies, investments in infrastructure, professional training, innovation and sustainability. Local, regional and national authorities, together with local communities, play a fundamental role in realizing these objectives.

Basilicata context

Starting from the regional demographics, the total resident population in Basilicata as of 31 July 2023 is approximately 534 thousand units, down by 0.7% compared to 2020 (-3,962 individuals) and by 6.4% compared to 2011 [7]. In the two-year period, the trend, already recorded in recent years, of population decline is confirmed due both to an almost zero natural rate and to very high internal migratory flows. As regards the type of population in decline, the negative natural balance mainly concerns the younger generations who study, but also the non-schooled population and adults.

As regards the urban fabric, Basilicata is a region that can still be defined as rural from the point of view of human settlements and the size of its urban fabric, as demonstrated by the absence of large centres: the two capital municipalities are included among the 60 and 70 thousand inhabitants and the other 129 municipalities overwhelmingly have a population of less than 5 thousand inhabitants. Residents in the inner areas - which cover more than 80% of the Lucanian territory - represent just under two thirds of the regional population, a figure four times higher than in the south and even eight times higher than the national average. Between 1951 and 2016, the Lucanian population decreased overall by approximately 9%, mainly due to the dynamics of the internal areas, where the population decreased by approximately a quarter. The decline more than offset the increase in urban areas, where the population almost doubled.

As regards the employment market, the phase of general improvement in labor market conditions has continued in Basilicata since 2016; the employment rate is 43% for women and 70% for men, while the employment rate of new graduates amounts to 35.8% of the population aged 20-34 years, with a youth unemployment rate of

23,7% [6]. The Basilicata, compared to other Italian regions, presents a limited diversification of the employment market and a strong tendency towards worker migration towards more developed urban centres. In 2022, the labor market experienced a strong stagnation, after the recovery that took place in 2021, which resulted in pre-pandemic employment levels being exceeded. The trend was heterogeneous between sectors: as in the rest of the country, the expansion of employment in services and construction continued, while their number was reduced in industry in the strict sense, affected by the slightly negative evolution of the sector. Specifically, with reference to the productive fabric, as of 30 June 2022, there were 60,575 companies registered in the Basilicata company register of the, of which 53,464 were active. 31.8% of the registered companies operate in the agriculture sector, 22.4% in the trade sector, 25.5% in the services sector, 12% in the construction sector and 8.2% in the industrial sector [4].

As regards the social fabric, Basilicata is one of the most virtuous regions from the point of view of access to and retention in school (low dropout, good offer of teaching hours and canteens), but still behind in terms of quality and innovation. The school dropout rate is 10.3%, lower than the Italian average of 14.7% and in line with the maximum threshold of 10% set by the European Union in 2020 (although still far from the objective of 5% for 2030). It is among the regions that has recorded the greatest progress over time, reducing the percentage of early school leavers by 15 points in 15 years (from 2000 to 2015), and it is the only region in the South to having already reached the 10% target by 2020. Despite these positive aspects in the school sector, there is no shortage of critical issues regarding the quality of infrastructure and supplementary services. 51% of adolescents attend schools with insufficient infrastructure to guarantee learning and 31% of classrooms are not yet equipped with fast internet connection. Finally, educational programs to encourage the acquisition of digital skills by minors are very limited. In fact, Basilicata, together with Piedmont, is the region with the lowest percentage of technological equipment in primary schools [9]. As regards university training and research, despite the presence of a university on average in terms of quality compared to small Italian universities, there is no shortage of positive experiences: to counteract this trend, Basilicata is in fact the first region in Italy to have started a path, through a public tender aimed at encouraging technological transfer from the research system to the production system. The Macchia Romana Campus of the University of Basilicata hosts the T3 Innovation, a technology transfer structure created in collaboration with international and national partners and a Basilicata Development Company Incubator, a coworking space where business and the world of research come together relation.

Finally, as regards the use of the internet at a regional level, there is a number of users equal to 73.8% of the population between 16 and 74 years old. The availability of a stable and fast Internet connection is one of the crucial elements on which the digital transition is based. However, not all families are equally ready for this transition and there is still a significant number of families who do not have access to the Internet at home: if in Italy these constitute 23.9 percent of families, in Basilicata this share rises to 31 .0 percent of households. It should also be noted that while in Italy 74.7 percent of families who use the Internet can count on a broadband connection, in Basilicata this share drops to 67.5 percent. Among families who do not use the Internet, 58.3 percent declare that no member knows how to use it, 21.2 percent believe that the Internet is not useful and/or interesting; the corresponding values at national level are equal to 56.4 percent and 25.5 percent respectively. Internet users aged 6 years and over amount to 63.1 percent, with a gap of 7 percentage points compared to the national average (70.4); the difference relating to the share of people who declare that they use the Internet every day is more limited (49.4 percent in Basilicata, 54.7 percent in Italy) [8].

SWOT ANALYSIS

Methodology

For the realization of the SWOT analysis in terms of remote working in Basilicata, 3 different categories were examined: 1. Workers; 2. Companies; 3. Territory.

1. WORKERS

Below is the SWOT analysis in terms of remote working in Basilicata for the "workers" category:

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + geographical reconnection with family/country of origin; + employment in internal areas; + self and time management; + well-being and quality of life; + opportunity to work in a unique mountain environment; + possibility of being able to enjoy the beauty of the landscape during work breaks; + soft and digital skills (stress and well-being management, effective communication, IT competence, technological problem solving); - transport costs; - days of the working week. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + technical problems in the workplace (unstable internet connection, problems accessing company systems, hardware problems, home distances); + isolation and loneliness in the workplace; + communication distortion; - boundary between private and working life; - adequate support for workers (limited technical assistance); - company reference points.
THREATS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + competition with other workers from other regions; - safety in the workplace; - relational skills with other teams of workers; - rules on work organization; - integration with the local community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + possibility to work outside the region; + team working to collaborate with other entities remotely, increase; + awareness of one's potential; + training programs for young workers in the field of digitalisation; - weekly working days; + recognition of a quality work team in terms of digital skills; + autonomy and problem solving in relation to other work teams

Table 1. SWOT analysis, worker category applied to the Basilicata Region.

Considerations:

The trend that emerged from "People at Work 2022: A Global Workforce View", the annual dossier drawn up by the ADP Research Institute, which carried out a survey on a sample of Italians and Lucanians, is a greater use of smart working and the transition to a 4-day working week. 42% of Lucanian workers interviewed intend to move to a 4-day working week, intensifying the hours of work per day; Furthermore, 42% of Lucanian workers would accept a reduction in pay if it meant improving their work-life balance. Furthermore, the research revealed that three-quarters of the Basilicata employees interviewed (75%) say they have considered changing jobs in the last 12 months. Of these, one in three (33%) has thought about changing sectors, 17% have thought about taking a sabbatical while another 17% have thought about opening a company or taking a temporary break from work, while less than one out of ten have considered the possibility of early retirement (8%). The balance between private life and working life is one of the issues that is most influencing the debate on the remote working world in the region (**Table 1**): the pandemic has given rise to new needs among workers, which companies must take into consideration and integrate into their employee recruitment and management strategy, if they do not want to be penalized in terms of attractiveness towards new talents and resources.

2. COMPANIES

Below is the SWOT analysis in terms of remote working in Basilicata for the "companies" category:

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + satisfaction for employees; + working productivity; + presence of sector companies in marginalized areas; - costs for company workplaces; - company costs (workers, safety). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + problems with connection infrastructures in the perimeter of internal areas; + organizational difficulties in terms of control and management of work activities; + location of workers; - company planning with workers.
THREATS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaboration between workers of a single team; + brain drain; - control of IT security systems; - support for companies in internal territories with poor digitalisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + access to global talent; + possibility of diversifying workers from a technical and cultural point of view; + markets for digital innovation in marginal areas (clusters, business associations or ICT companies) + creation of physical technological systems that use digital.

Table 2. SWOT analysis, companies' category applied to the Basilicata Region.

Considerations:

The fourth commission (Social Policy) of the Basilicata Regional Council approved, last February 2023, the bill "Support measures for agile working or smart working" (initiative of councilor Luca Braia). The objective of the law is to support, also at a regional level, the evolution of Smart Working by guaranteeing adequate support to workers and employers in order to increase awareness and the necessary skills, also in terms of online security (**Table 2**); support company planning; expand the benefits of smart working and worker protections (avoiding technostress, overworking and underemployment). The bill consists of 9 articles: article 1 defines the terms 'agile working' and its peculiarities compared to 'teleworking'; in article 2 the objectives of the regulation are declared, aimed at promoting 'agile working'; in article 3 the support actions for workers, new hires and companies for the increase of 'smart working' are given in detail; in article 4 the Regional Observatory on Agile Working is established, and its tasks are defined, including the drafting of a Regional Plan for the promotion of agile working; Article 5 establishes the Regional Fund for smart working; Article 6 lists the requirements for accessing the benefits; Article 7 contains the financial rule; while articles 8 and 9 indicate the State Aid rule and its entry into force respectively [10].

3. TERRITORY

Below is the SWOT analysis in terms of remote working in Basilicata for the "territory" category:

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - depopulation of internal areas; - pollution of the mountain areas where work activities take place; + number of new inhabitants; + regional employment rate; + regional policy measures to support the competitiveness of SMEs (including digitalisation); + regional youth employment; + regional digital and creative businesses; + technological infrastructures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - connection infrastructures; - services and incentives for working families; - smart work spaces; - corporate training on technological tools; - financial support for the strengthening of the technological park; - workers with an average age of 19-35 years with consequent current limit of employees in the use of cutting-edge digital tools; - attractiveness due to lack of infrastructure;
THREATS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduction of social capital (less interactions between people); + risk of losing the typical characteristics of the mountain environment: silence, tranquillity, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + possibility of attracting workers from outside; + fight against depopulation, increasing presences in the Lucanian municipalities; + consumption and the economic balance sheet of the entire regional area + "seasonal adjustment" for hospitality activities which in periods other than those in which the hospitality activity is carried out by welcoming workers in agile working mode; + recognition of the profile of the University of Basilicata as a subject of scientific excellence in training and research in ICT technologies. + scholarship systems shared with companies for young people and international students (including doctoral students and researchers) in different sectors in order to increase their attractiveness.

Table 3. SWOT analysis, territory category applied to the Basilicata Region.

Considerations:

The use of smart working in Basilicata offers new opportunities for the most marginal areas, such as internal areas, which could become attractors of stability for many families. Basilicata, in this context, being a region with a prevalence of small municipalities, can become a prototype of an innovative experimentation relating to the use of smart working, as a central element of digital innovation, attraction of skills, repopulation and respect for workers and 'environment. A necessary condition is the construction of a network of services and incentives (**Table 3**) with which more and more families can find the most suitable and attractive location in Basilicata to carry out their work in an agile way. A real lever for lasting growth, capable of guaranteeing economic profitability, corporate reorganization and relaunch, greater well-being and development of society itself, promoting social, territorial and economic cohesion and reducing the current growing inequalities.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, remote working offers a series of significant opportunities for the mountain areas of Basilicata. These opportunities concern improving the quality of life, promoting sustainability, valorising cultural heritage, flexibility in the use of natural resources and economic diversification. These mountain regions, with their unique natural and cultural heritage, offer a particular context in which remote working could have a significant impact. The Basilicata mountain areas are often characterized by a high quality of life, which is an aspect of considerable relevance both for residents and for regional authorities interested in preserving and promoting the well-being of local communities. Remote working in these regions contributes to promoting environmental sustainability. Reducing the need for daily travel leads to a decrease in environmental impact, including the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and road congestion. Furthermore, in mountain areas, often with less developed road infrastructures, remote working helps preserve natural resources and ensure more sustainable mobility. In addition, dependence on specific sectors, often related to agriculture or seasonal tourism, can be reduced through remote working, opening up new job opportunities in technology, service sectors, and more. This can contribute to greater economic stability in mountain regions, mitigating vulnerability related to economic cycles.

However, there are significant challenges to consider. First, the issue of Internet connectivity emerges as a crucial barrier to the effective adoption of remote working. Basilicata, being a less developed region in terms of digital infrastructure compared to metropolitan areas, requires significant investments to improve connectivity and guarantee reliable broadband throughout the territory. Without a fast and stable connection, remote working may not be viable for many occupations, excluding some communities from participating in remote working, creating socio-economic gaps.

Ultimately, remote working in Basilicata offers promising prospects, but requires a well-thought-out strategy that addresses the specificities of the region, such as connectivity, social isolation and technological dependence. The adoption of digital infrastructure development and worker support policies can help maximize the benefits of remote working, while promoting the economic and social development of the region.

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